

The Role of Information Accesibility on Welfare Achievement: Evidence of Internet Using in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Published Online: June 10, 2025

More than 3 decades information variable has been known as total factor productivity (TFP) which accompanied by labor and physical capital is very significant in enhancing productivity . The contribution of internet usage to reduce the level of disparity among regions in Indonesia has not been evaluated in improving welfare through laveraging productivity, especially those related to the role of the age group of its users. This study aims to elucidate the influence of geographic zones and age groups on welfare achievements in the following year (HDI_{t+1}). The OLS model was applied at a confidence level of >95%. The predictor variables are; (1) Geographical zones use dummy variables in 3 categories based on the Wallacea and Weber Lines, namely the East zone [D_EAST] and the West zone (D_WEST] with the Central zone as the reference; (2) Age group variables use the proportion of adulthood [ADUL], adolescence [ADOLC], and teenager [TEEN]. In addition, to control residual errors, the achievement of the current HDI [HDI_t] is also accounted in the model. Data from 35 provinces in 2021 and 2022 were acquired from the official website of the National Statistic Agency (www.bps.go.id). Model parameter optimization uses Minitab16. This result suggests that [HDI]_{t+1}: is not significantly influenced by the regional division zone, and is very significantly influenced by the user's age group with parameter sensitivities of 4.488 (p = 0.046), 4.479 (p = 0.047), and 4.485 (p = 0.046) respectively. Development planners do not need to make policy discrimination based on differences zones and age groups of users in efforts to increase HDI.

KEYWORDS:

adult, adolenscent, teenager, HDI, TFP, Wallacea Line, Weber Line

INTRODUCTION

Since the early 20th century, the economic dicourse has been undergoing significant transformation, especially with the notion of Ronald Coase who emphasized transaction cost as factor of critical in economic process (Coase, 1937). The Coase' work set the stage for acknowledging information variable as crucial production factor beyond classical inputs namely the capital and labor. This recognition foudner theoritical rooting in Solow's economic growth model, which unexplained the residual of economic growth based on the classical inputs. As mention by Kryszak et al (2021) later

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**Cite this Article: Ida Nurhaida, Andi Windah, Samsul Bakri (2025). The Role of Information Accesibility on Welfare Achievement: Evidence of Internet Using in Indonesia. International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 5(6), 556-562*

known the unexplained growth residu is understood as Total Factor Productivity (TFP), then attributed to improve knowledege, technology and especially information accesibility (Bakri et al, 2024).

Recent empirical evidence support this shift. According to Hjort et al (2021) that the penetration of high speed internet in some African countries have increased job around 4.2% particularly in services sectors. Whereas in Indonesia in between 2010-2020 periods of significant digital manufacture expantion coincided with average GDP growth around of 5-6% (World Bank, 2023).

In the digital erra, the mastery of information defines market competation win. Not only does in industrial manufacturing or service sectors, but also in traditional agriculture sector (Bakri et al, 2024), where access to real-time market price or weather in forecasting can drastically alter ouput efficiency in any production process (Nugroho et al, 2022). More over, the productivity enhancement in developing countries are often

control not by capital investment but by better information availability (Dabla-Norris et al, 2023).

Historically, the gobal GDP per capita was relatively in flat curve until the Industrial Revolution. From 1900 to 2000, however, the wolrd economy grew by more than 20 times in term of GDP per capita. While in 21st century, digital technology contribute over 25% of global productivity gains (Brynjolfsson et al, 2022).

The culmination of information role is most evident in internet usage that nowadays embedded in almost all aspect of individual or comunity life. While the use internet for liesure or entertainment has sparked conceren about overuse, but some studies show it can have net positive effects on creativity and emotional well being, which susequently enhance productity as well (Liu et al, 2023). More over, empirical research has link enhanced eductaion attainment, and in turn much more has contributed the poverty reduction program including in rural regions (Bergiantino et al, 2025).

Indonesia expirienced rapid digitalizations since the late of 1990s. By 2024, the internet penetration rate reached 79.5%, amounting to 221.6 million users (AJII, 2024). This surge has paralld improvement in the human development index (HDI) which rose from 71.94 in 2014 to 75.05 in 2024 (BPS, 2025). It is prove that internet usage has been enhancing people welfare. The internet has reshaped public service delivery almost all sectors including education and health care reach out to rural regions (Aisyah et al, 2024). In relation to this role according to Bala (2024) that region with better internet penetration has shown higher welfare in term of Human Development Index.

Dispite of those national-level in the welfare achivement, the disparity remain in Indonesia due to large descripancies in its geogaphically distribution. Particularly in Easteren region such as Papua, NTT, Maluku, still lags in infrastructure and people digital literay than this descripancies impacting in welfare achivement level. Fatika (2024) shows that internet penetration in eastern region is lower around 20-30% than that of Java or Sumatera. But Java Island has penetratrion more than 80%. Beside the penetration level, the role of the age group of internet users also greatly determines the level of productivity which in turn will determine their achievement of welfare (Xiong, 2024). The proportion internet user in Indonesia among the age maturity is 20.3, 24.8, and 54.9 pецents for teenager, adolenscent, an adult respectively. This distribution is accompanied by an HDI achievement of 73.8 (BPS, 2025).

Buliding on the rational above, this study is aimed to:

- [1] Compare the influence of geograpic zone (Easteren, Central, and Western Indonesia) on the following year's HDI achivement (HDI_{t+1}),
- [2] Quantify the proportional impact of internet use across age group (the teenager, adolescent, and adult) on the $[HDI]_{t+1}$.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study was conducted at the Forest Inventory and Management Laboratory (*Lab IPH*), University of Lampung, from February to April 2025. Ordinary Least Square was applied at a confidence level of >95%. Mathematically, this model is presented in Eq. {1} below.

$$[HDI]_{i,t+1} = \beta_0 + \beta_1[D_EAST]_{i,t} + \beta_2[D_WEST]_{i,t} + \beta_3[TEEN]_{i,t} + \beta_4[ADOLSC]_{i,t} + \beta_5[ADULT]_{i,t} + \beta_6[HDI]_{i,t} + \xi_{i,t}$$

Eq. {1}

in Eq. {1} symbol $[D_EAST]$ =dummy West Region zone, $[D_WEST]$ =dummy West zone, $[ADULT]$, $[ADOLSC]$, and $[TEEN]$ are the proportion (%) of internet users for adult, young adult, and teenager groups, respectively. Where i =the number of province, t =year data, and ξ = residual error of the model.

Data were acquired from the official website of the Central Statistics Agency (www.bps.go.id). The input data preparation for the response variable is the 2022 HDI (HDI_{t+1}) data from 35 provinces in Indonesia. The input data to test the influence of regional zoning (Eastern, Central, and Western) uses a dummy variable, in this case the Central Zone as the reference. The division into 3 zones is based on the Wallacea and Webber Lines. The Central Zone is whole region in between the two lines (Figure 1).

The predictor variable for the proportion of internet users for 3 age groups (teenagers, adolescents, and adults) used is the 2021 data. To control residual error, the 2021 HDI (HDI_t) is also included as the predictor variabel in the model. Working Hypthoses:

$H_0: \beta_1=\beta_2=\beta_3=\beta_4=\beta_5=\beta_6=0$ (None of the variable significantly influncent the respon variable)

$H_1: \beta_1\neq\beta_2\neq\beta_3\neq\beta_4\neq\beta_5\neq\beta_6\neq 0$ (At least there will be one variable significantly influences the respon variable).

We employed Minitab 16 to achieve the best model parameter.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistic

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics of the proportion of internet users according to the division of 3 zones based on the Wallacea Line and the Weber Line. These two types of lines are the boundaries of geographical diversity that are estimated to cause innitial impact of natural productivity.

Hypotheses Test Result

The six predictor variables applied in this study together provide very good results and fit in predicting the magnitude

Ida Nurhaida et al, The Role of Information Accesibility on Welfare Achievement: Evidence of Internet Using in Indonesia

of HDI to be achieved in which is $P = 0.000$ which means it provides a level of confidence $> 99.99\%$ (Table 2).

The Role of 6 Predictor Variables

The next stage is to examine the influence of each of the six predictor variables applied in this study, as depicted in Table 3.

The Role of Geographycal Zone

Geographical zones are an expression of resource distribution. Initially it is a distribution of natural resources (Zhang et al, 2021), then if followed by investment for their exploitation it will be accompanied by a concentration of population (Deichmann et al, 2005) which also means a reflection of human resources availability along with the level of agglomeration of economic activities at the areas (Ellison et al, 1999). Subsistence exploitation of natural resources generally does not involve an intensive scale, so it almost never causes agglomeration of economic activities such as traditional farming, hunting, and manual mining of minerals without heavy equipment (Zhang et al, 2021).

When capital investment begins, accompanied by modern equipment, the exploitation of natural resources becomes massive, accompanied also by the use of heavy equipment (Meraj et al, 2021). In a state of subsistence exploitation, the level of community welfare is largely determined by the quality of natural resources (Alam et al, 2025). However, when economic activities begin to intensify, community welfare is more influenced by the trickling down effect of income from these modern sectors (Bravo-Ortega et al, 1999). In this situation, community income can also be multiplied by various forms of transactions as a result of the impact of the investment and the agglomeration of various forms of economic activities that grow following investment in the exploitation of natural resources (Alam et al, 2025). Currently, the level of natural resource exploitation has been almost even across the three geographical zones of Indonesia (Gunawan, 2023), which has implications for the decreasing gap in welfare achievement in the following year (HDI_{t+1}) which is a reflection of the decreasing level of income, consumption level, and knowledge level as found in this study (Table 3).

As can be seen in Table 3, that in relation to $[HDI]_{t+1}$, it turns out that in aggregate the quality of natural resources in the geographical zone of Eastern Indonesia [D_EAST] does not have a significant influence compared to Central Indonesia. Likewise with [D_WEST].

This finding indicates that even though initially the three zones bounded by the Wallacea Line and the Weber Line were very diverse natural resources, nowadays they no longer have an impact on disparities in people's welfare achievement accompanying the exploitation of natural resources accompanied by the agglomeration of economic activities (Dutu, 2015). Of course, with the development of the

economy activities, it is accompanied by increasing governance and various institutional arrangements that are increasingly improving as a necessary condition for reducing the discrepancy in welfare achievement among the three regions as founded by Hilmawan et al (2023).

The Role of Internet Penetration

The Internet as the third production input outside of physical capital and labor variables in increasing productivity in micro-individual humans or individual companies. When individuals increase their productivity, so does the aggregate as founded in OECD countries by Hsieh et al (2020). This means that it is also parallel with their income which is also government income through taxes. As a public service provider, the government acts as a stimulator of increasing individual and community income through public investment, which in turn trigger private invesment that also escalates individual and community income as well as welfare levels (Melayanti et al, 2021).

However, the impact of internet penetration can be influenced by the age group of user maturity. In Table 2, it can be checked that every 1% increase in the proportion of teenager, adolescent, and adulthood groups in year t can increase the achievement HDI in the following year (HDI_{t+1}) by 4.485 ($p=0.046$), 4.489 ($p=0.047$), & 4.479 ($p=0.046$) respectively. This fact indicates that adolescent group has the greatest sensitivity to HDH_{t+1} compared to the teenager [TEEN] group and the adulthood [ADULT] group.

In the digital era, internet usage has become an inseparable part of daily life for almost all levels of society, both for recreational activities and for work activities (Nguyen et al, 2023). These two types of activities can ultimately encourage creativity in increasing income, especially because the internet plays a role in reducing the information gap between parties and in reducing various forms of transaction costs (Yuliyanti et al, 2023). With this increase in income, it will have an impact on increasing individual welfare and the welfare of society as a whole (Wahyuni et al., 2022). However, the magnitude of the influence of the increase in internet usage is also greatly determined by the level of digital literacy of its users (Zhao et al, 2023).

The variables that greatly influence internet literacy include the age maturity group of users. According to Heponiemi et al (2023), the level of physical and cognitive function in older adults can predict their internet use and digital competence. Declining visual, physical, and cognitive functions with age can hinder an individual's ability to access and use digital technology effectively. In line with our finding, Pyżalski et al (2023) found that age differences affect the development of digital communication and information skills in Polish adolescents. Older age groups showed lower levels of digital skills, which can affect their ability to access and utilize digital information efficiently.

Gushevinalti et al (2023) reported that the elderly group in

Bengkulu City, Indonesia, had lower levels of digital literacy compared to the younger age group. This means that this age group shows that psychological and physical maturity play a role in an individual's level of internet literacy. As individuals age, they may face additional challenges in accessing and using digital technology, which can affect their ability to utilize the internet effectively.

In contrast, the findings in our study could also be the opposite, that the teenager age group also indicated lower internet usefulness in obtaining and utilizing information. It, therefore, resulted in relatively lower welfare achievements in the following year (HDI_{t+1}) when teenager penetration by one percent in any region as reported by Camerini et al (2022).

The Carry-over Effect of Current HDI

Indonesia was declared an upper middle income country in 2022 after its Gross National Income (GNI) per capita was recorded at USD 4,580, an increase of 9.8% compared to the previous year of USD 4,170. This increase puts Indonesia back into the upper middle income category, although the threshold for this classification has also increased due to global inflation (Ministry of Finance RI, 2023).

This means that Indonesia is transitioning from an agrarian economy to an industrial country. During this transition period, the acceleration of per capita income growth began to decline, which is also in line with the decline in the acceleration of the HDI. According to BPS (2025), in the period 2020 to 2024, the increase in HDI was 0.35, 0.62, 0.86, and back to 0.63. This report reflexes the slowdown in productivity growth in this transition phase is generally because almost all resources have been used. This claim was also found from the results of our research, that the current year's HDI (HDI_t) only has a parameter sensitivity of 0.982 ($p = 0.000$). This figure is only below a quarter of the lowest internet penetration contribution of 4.479 ($p = 0.047$). This means that in the transition process, technological input is the keyword because almost all natural resources and human resources have been optimally utilized. The use of information technology has increased Total Factor Productivity, accelerated income, and ultimately increased the achievement of the following year's HDI (HDI_{t+1}) faster.

CONCLUSION

This result suggests that the next year human development index [HDI_{t+1}]:

- (1) will not significantly be influenced by the regional division zone, and
- (2) will very significantly be influenced by the user's age group with parameter sensitivities of 4.488 ($p = 0.046$), 4.479 ($p = 0.047$), and 4.485 ($p = 0.046$), respectively.

It is recommend that development planners do not need to make any policy discrimination based on differences zones and age groups of users in every efforts to increase [HDI_{t+1}].

DISCLAIMER

We, the authors, are not in conflicting of interest with this research result.

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Figure 1. Grouping of provinces in Indonesia into 3 zones based on the Wallace Line (blue one) and the Weber Line (purple one).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistic

Geographical Zone	Statistic	Age Group Maturity of Internet User (%)			Welfare Achievement	
		Teenager	Adolescent	Adulthood	[HDI] ₂₀₂₁	[HDI] ₂₀₂₂
Western	Max	25.0	29.8	65.6	82.3	82.8
	Min	15.9	18.2	50.2	69.0	69.7
	Average	20.5	23.6	55.9	74.2	74.7
	Sd	2.30	2.77	3.84	3.01	2.99
Central	Max	23.52	30.85	58.15	74.03	74.52
	Min	18.02	23.30	47.84	67.02	67.63
	Average	21.12	27.42	51.47	70.76	71.37
	Sd	2.10	2.53	3.13	2.33	2.30

Eastern	Max	19.50	28.74	60.38	71.55	72.04
	Min	15.22	23.81	52.28	61.40	62.16
	Average	17.68	26.38	55.94	67.16	67.80
	Sd	2.01	2.65	3.46	4.45	4.36

Table 2. Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Regresssion	6	474,984	79.164	11520.44	0.000
Residual Error	25	0.172	0.007		
Total	31	475,155			

Table 3. The role of internet use in the next HDI achievement

Predictor	Symbol	Coef.	SE	T	P
Constant	-	-	213.8	-	0.04
		446.7		2.09	7
Dummy Wallacea Zone (Middle Zone=0)					
Eastern (1 if eastern, 0 if others)	[D_EAS T] _{i,t}	-	0.0640	-	0,75
		0.020	7	0.32	2
		5			
Western(1 if western, 0 if others)	[D_WES T] _{i,t}	0.023	0.0437	0.53	0,60
		3	7		0
User Age Maturity Group					
Teenager	[TEEN] i,t	4.485	2.139	2.10	0,04
					6
Adolescent	[ADOLS C] _{i,t}	4.479	2.139	2.09	0,04
					7
Adulthood	[ADULT] _{i,t}	4.488	2.140	2.10	0,04
					6
Current Year HDI	[HDI] _{i,t}	0.982	0.0059	164.	0.00
		4	7	5	0
S = 0.0828951			R-Sq =	R-Sq(adj)=	
			100.0%	99.9%	